

Kepler's Laws as Properties of the Kinematic Equations of Motion of a Point Along Second-Order Curves

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Abstract

Johannes Kepler empirically established three laws of celestial mechanics. In the scientific literature, Kepler's laws are usually derived using dynamical variables. This paper shows that Kepler's laws are consequences of the kinematic equations of an ellipse. The derivation of the formulas is carried out for two variants of the motion of a mathematical point: relative to the focus and relative to the center of the ellipse. Numerical examples are presented.

Keywords: ellipse; focus; center; Kepler's laws.

I. Motion of a Point Along an Ellipse Relative to the Focus

Point M moves along an ellipse, starting from aphelion (A).

Fig. 1

We consider a system of equations of a parametric pendulum (1.1), where time (t) is the parameter.

$$\begin{cases} x = r(\varphi(t)) \cdot \cos(\varphi(t)) \\ y = r(\varphi(t)) \cdot \sin(\varphi(t)) \end{cases} \quad (1.1)$$

Substitute into system (1) the radius of the ellipse relative to the focus:

$$r(\varphi(t)) = \frac{b^2}{a(1-e \cdot \cos(\varphi(t)))} \quad (1.2)$$

$$\begin{cases} x = \frac{b^2}{a(1-e*\cos(\varphi(t)))} * \cos(\varphi(t)) \\ y = \frac{b^2}{a(1-e*\cos(\varphi(t)))} * \sin(\varphi(t)) \end{cases} \quad (1.3)$$

Differentiate twice. We obtain the coordinates of velocity and acceleration:

$$\dot{x} = \frac{d}{dt} \left(r(\varphi(t)) \cos(\varphi(t)) \right) = -\frac{b^2 * \dot{\varphi} * \sin(\varphi(t))}{a(e*\cos(\varphi(t))-1)^2} = \frac{r^2 * \dot{\varphi} * \sin(\varphi(t))}{e*\cos(\varphi(t))-1} \quad (1.4)$$

$$\dot{y} = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{p}{1-e*\cos(\varphi(t))} \sin(\varphi(t)) \right) = \frac{b^2 * \dot{\varphi} * (-e+\cos(\varphi(t)))}{a(e*\cos(\varphi(t))-1)^2} = \frac{r^2 * \dot{\varphi} * (-e+\cos(\varphi(t)))}{1-e*\cos(\varphi(t))} \quad (1.5)$$

$$\ddot{x} = \frac{b^2 \left((-e*\cos(\varphi(t))*\sin(\varphi(t))+\sin(\varphi(t)))\dot{\varphi} + \dot{\varphi}^2 \left(e*\cos(\varphi(t))^2 - 2e + \cos(\varphi(t)) \right) \right)}{a(e*\cos(\varphi(t))-1)^3} \quad (1.6)$$

$$\ddot{y} = \frac{-b^2 \left((-\cos(\varphi(t))(e*\cos(\varphi(t))-1)+e)\dot{\varphi} + 2\dot{\varphi}^2 \left(e^2 - \frac{e*\cos(\varphi(t))+1}{2} \right) \sin(\varphi(t)) \right)}{a(e*\cos(\varphi(t))-1)^3} \quad (1.7)$$

$$\text{Velocity: } v = \sqrt{\dot{x}^2 + \dot{y}^2} = \frac{b^2 * \dot{\varphi} * \sqrt{1+e^2-2e*\cos \varphi(t)}}{a(-1+e*\cos \varphi(t))^2} = \frac{r * \dot{\varphi} * \sqrt{1+e^2-2e*\cos \varphi(t)}}{(1-e*\cos \varphi(t))} \quad (1.8)$$

$$\text{Acceleration: } \dot{v} = \sqrt{\ddot{x}^2 + \ddot{y}^2} =$$

$$b^2 \left(\begin{array}{l} \frac{\sqrt{(e^2-2e*\cos(\varphi(t))+1)(e*\cos(\varphi(t))-1)^2 * \dot{\varphi}^2}}{a(e*\cos(\varphi(t))-1)^3} + \\ \frac{\sqrt{4 \left(e^2 - \frac{3*e*\cos(\varphi(t))+1}{2} \right) \dot{\varphi}^2 (e*\cos(\varphi(t)) \sin(\varphi(t))-1) \dot{\varphi}}}{a(e*\cos(\varphi(t))-1)^3} - \\ \frac{\sqrt{4\dot{\varphi}^4 \left(-\cos(\varphi(t))^3 e^3 + \left(e^4 - \frac{e^2}{4} \right) \cos(\varphi(t))^2 + \left(e^3 + \frac{e}{2} \right) \cos(\varphi(t)) - e^4 - \frac{1}{4} \right)}}{a(e*\cos(\varphi(t))-1)^3} \end{array} \right) \quad (1.9)$$

Form a system of equations from (1.6), (1.7) and solve with respect to $\ddot{\varphi}$: We obtain the kinematic equation of motion of a point relative to the focus along second-order curves:

$$\ddot{\varphi} = \frac{2*e*\sin(\varphi)*\dot{\varphi}^2}{1-e*\cos(\varphi)} \quad (1.10)$$

For different values of the eccentricity, the type of curve changes.

In astronomical tables, time is measured in Earth units. The period $T = 1$ Earth year. Distances are measured in astronomical units.

Kepler's First Law

Kepler's first law is satisfied a priori, since equations (1.10) describe motion along an ellipse.

Kepler's Second Law (Law of Areas)

Kepler's second law states that the radius vector drawn from the focus of the orbit to the moving point sweeps out equal areas in equal intervals of time. In polar coordinates (r, φ) with the focus at the origin, this is expressed as:

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = \frac{1}{2} r^2 \frac{d\varphi}{dt} = \text{const} \quad (1.11)$$

$$\text{where } r(\varphi(t)) = \frac{b^2}{a(1-e*\cos(\varphi(t)))} \quad (1.12)$$

Equation (1.10) can be rewritten in a form convenient for integration. Note that it can be reduced to the form:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\ln \left(\frac{d\varphi}{dt} \right) \right) = \frac{2*e*\sin(\varphi(t))}{1-e*\cos(\varphi(t))} \cdot \frac{d\varphi}{dt} \quad (1.13)$$

Integrating with respect to time, we obtain:

$$\frac{d\varphi}{dt} = C(1 - e \cos(\varphi(t)))^2 \quad (1.14)$$

where C is the constant of integration.

Now we use the expression for $r(\varphi(t)) = \frac{b^2}{a(1-e*\cos(\varphi(t)))}$. Then, simplifying, we obtain:

$$r^2 \frac{d\varphi}{dt} = \left(\frac{b^2}{a(1-e*\cos(\varphi(t)))} \right)^2 \cdot C_1(1 - e \cos(\varphi(t)))^2 \quad (1.15)$$

Since a, b, C are constants, it follows that:

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = \frac{1}{2} r^2 \frac{d\varphi}{dt} = \text{const} \quad (1.16)$$

Kepler's Third Law

From (1.14) $\dot{\varphi}(t) = \frac{d\varphi}{dt} = C(1 - e \cos(\varphi(t)))^2$.

1. Initial formulas (motion relative to the focus)

For elliptical motion relative to the focus, the following are used:

Radius vector (1.2) $(\varphi(t)) = \frac{p}{1-e*\cos(\varphi(t))}$, $p = a(1 - e^2)$;

Angular velocity (1.14) $\dot{\varphi} = C(1 - e)^2$.

2. Formula for linear velocity

The magnitude of the linear velocity.

The general formula for linear velocity in polar coordinates. For any plane curve $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{r}(\varphi)$ it is valid that: $v = \sqrt{\dot{\mathbf{r}}^2 + (r\dot{\varphi})^2}$

When is it acceptable to write $v = r\dot{\varphi}$ (1.17)

provided that $\dot{r} = 0$. This means that:

- the motion is perpendicular to the radius;
- the velocity is directed along the tangent, orthogonal to the radius.

At perihelion and aphelion of the ellipse (focal system), these conditions are satisfied.

Substituting (1.2) and (1.14) into (1.17), we obtain:

$$v = \frac{p}{1 - e \cdot \cos(\varphi(t))} C(1 - e)^2$$

$$v = Cp(1 - e \cos \varphi) \quad (1.18)$$

This is the general analytical formula for the linear velocity.

3. Linear velocity at perihelion ($\varphi = 0$) $\cos 0 = 1$

$$\text{From (1.18), taking into account } v_p = Ca(1 - e)^2(1 + e) \quad (1.19)$$

4. Linear velocity at aphelion ($\varphi = \pi$) $\cos \pi = -1$

$$\text{From (1.18), taking into account } v_a = Ca(1 + e)^2(1 - e) \quad (1.20)$$

Determination of C through the period T

$$T = \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{d\varphi}{\dot{\varphi}}$$

Substituting (1.14):

$$T = \frac{1}{C} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{d\varphi}{(1 - e \cos(\varphi(t)))^2} \quad (1.21)$$

A known analytical integral:

$$\int_0^{2\pi} \frac{d\varphi}{(1 - e \cos(\varphi(t)))^2} = \frac{2\pi}{(1 - e^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \quad (1.22)$$

Substituting (1.22) into (1.21), we obtain:

$$C = \frac{2\pi}{T(1-e^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \quad (1.23)$$

Let us denote the difference of linear velocities:

$$v_p - v_a = \delta \quad (1.24)$$

The sectorial velocity, according to the law of conservation of angular momentum, is a constant:

$$v_s = 1/2 \mathbf{v} \mathbf{r} \quad (1.25)$$

We express the sectorial velocity through the magnitude of the linear velocity.

Since $\sin(v_p \wedge \mathbf{r}_p) = \sin(v_a \wedge \mathbf{r}_a) = 1$, we obtain:

$$v_s = 1/2 v_p r_p = 1/2 r_p (v_a + \delta) \quad (1.26)$$

$$v_s = 1/2 v_a r_a \quad (1.27)$$

$$1/2 r_p (v_a + \delta) = 1/2 r_a v_a \quad (1.28)$$

$$v_a = \frac{r_p \delta}{r_a - r_p} \rightarrow \frac{v_a}{v_p} = \frac{r_p}{r_a} \quad (1.29)$$

Substituting (1.29) into (1.27), we get:

$$v_s = \frac{\delta r_p r_a}{2(r_a - r_p)} \quad (1.30)$$

Let us compute the area of the ellipse. On the one hand:

$$S_{\text{ellipse}} = \pi ab \quad (1.31)$$

where a is the length of the semi-major axis and b is the length of the semi-minor axis of the orbit.

On the other hand:

$$S_{\text{ellipse}} = v_s T = T \frac{\delta r_p r_a}{2(r_a - r_p)} \quad (1.32)$$

Hence:

$$T \frac{\delta r_p r_a}{2(r_a - r_p)} = \pi ab \quad (1.33)$$

For further transformations, we use the geometric properties of the ellipse. We have the relations ...

Substituting into (1.33), we obtain:

$$T \frac{\delta b^2}{4ae} = \pi ab \quad (1.34)$$

$$T \frac{\delta b}{a^2 e} = 4\pi ; \quad \text{где } T = 1; \quad (1.35)$$

$$\frac{\delta b}{4\pi a^2 e} = 1 \quad (1.36)$$

$$\text{Kepler's third law: } \frac{T^2}{a^3} = 1 \quad (1.37)$$

$$T = \sqrt{a^3} \quad (1.38)$$

$$\frac{\delta b}{4\pi a^2 e} = \frac{T^2}{a^3}, \frac{\delta b}{4\pi e} = \frac{T^2}{a}, T = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\delta b a}{\pi e}} = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{(v_p - v_a) b a}{\pi e}} \quad (1.39)$$

Formula (1.39) expresses the orbital period exclusively through the geometric parameters of the ellipse and numerically determined kinematic quantities, which makes it possible to use it for an independent numerical verification of Kepler's third law.

The formula is valid under the condition that the linear velocities are obtained on the same time scale consistent with the equation of motion.

In this article, this condition is satisfied because:

v_p, v_a are obtained from the numerical solution of the same equation (1.10);

time t is the same for all quantities;

the time scale does not change during comparison.

The lengths of the orbital semi-axes are given in astronomical units (au), and the orbital period is expressed in (*Earth years*). This choice of units corresponds to the standard normalization of Kepler's third law, which implies that the relationship $T^2 = a^3$ holds for the motion of planets around the Sun,

where T is expressed in Earth years (Earth year), and the semi-axes a and b are expressed in astronomical units (au). The time scale is fixed such that the formula $T = \sqrt{a^3}$ holds without additional coefficients. Therefore, the period calculated using formula (1.39) is directly expressed in Earth years and can be correctly compared with the classical form of Kepler's third law.

v_p, v_a are calculated using formulas (1.19-1.20).

Numerical examples for a model ellipse and for the planets Mercury, Venus, Earth, and Mars confirm the agreement with the classical form of Kepler's third law.

Example 1. Let us set $a = 9$; $b = 7$.

$$a = 9.00, b = 7.00$$

$$e = 0.62853938$$

$$r_1 = 14.656856 \quad r_2 = 0.0000000$$

$$v_p = 118.40350 \quad v_a = 27.007179$$

$$r_a = 14.656856 \quad r_p = 3.3431456$$

$$T = \sqrt{a^3} = 27.000000$$

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{(v_p - v_a)ba}{\pi e}} = 26.999981$$

$$27.000000 \approx 26.999981$$

Example 2. Mercury

$$a = 0.39 \text{ [au]}, b = 0.38 \text{ [au]}$$

$$T = \sqrt{a^3} = 0.24084271 \text{ [Earth year]}$$

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{(v_p - v_a)ba}{\pi e}} = 0.24084280 \text{ [Earth year]}$$

$$0.24084271 \approx 0.24084280 \text{ [Earth year]}$$

Example 3. Venus

$$a = 0.73 \text{ [au]}, b = 0.73 \text{ [au]}$$

$$e = 6.80000009E-03$$

$$T = \sqrt{a^3} = 0.62144679 \text{ [Earth year]}$$

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{(v_p - v_a)ba}{\pi e}} = 0.62116992 \text{ [Earth year]}$$

$$0.62144679 \approx 0.62116992 \text{ [Earth year]}$$

Example 4. Earth

$$a = 1.00 \text{ [au]}, b = 0.99986297 \text{ [au]}$$

$$e = 1.67112295E-02$$

$$T = \sqrt{a^3} = 1.0000039 \text{ [Earth year]}$$

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{(v_p - v_a)ba}{\pi e}} = 1.0000157 \text{ [Earth year]}$$

Example 5. Mars

$$a = 1.52 \text{ [au]}, b = 1.52 \text{ [au]}$$

$$e = 9.33941007E-02$$

$$T = \sqrt{a^3} = 1.8807580 \text{ [Earth year]}$$

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{(v_p - v_a)ba}{\pi e}} = 1.8807570 \text{ [Earth year]}$$

$$1.8807580 \approx 1.8807570 \text{ [Earth year]}$$

II. Motion of a Point Along an Ellipse Relative to the Center

The origin of coordinates is at the center of the ellipse (Fig. 2). The radius function changes.

Fig. 2

The kinematic equation of motion of a point relative to the center along second-order curves is derived analogously to equation (1.10), with the radius formula (1.2) replaced by (2.3):

$$\frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} = \frac{2e^2 \cos(\theta(t)) \sin(\theta(t)) \left(\frac{d\theta}{dt}\right)^2}{1 - e^2 \cos(\theta(t))^2} \quad (2.1)$$

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = \frac{1}{2} r^2 \frac{d\theta}{dt} = \text{const}, \quad (2.2)$$

$$\text{где } r(\theta(t)) = \frac{b}{\sqrt{1 - e^2 \cos^2 \theta(t)}} \quad (2.3)$$

Kepler's Second Law

Transform equation (2.1) by dividing both sides by $\frac{d\theta}{dt}$ (assuming $\frac{d\theta}{dt} \neq 0$).

$$\frac{1}{\frac{d\theta}{dt}} \cdot \frac{d^2\theta}{dt^2} = \frac{2e^2 \cos(\theta(t)) \sin(\theta(t)) \frac{d\theta}{dt}}{1 - e^2 \cos(\theta(t))}$$

Note that the left-hand side is $\frac{d}{dt} \left(\ln \left(\frac{d\theta}{dt} \right) \right)$, and the right-hand side is the time derivative of $\ln(1 - e^2 \cos(\theta)^2)$, since:

The left-hand side becomes the time derivative of $\frac{d}{dt} \left(\ln \left(\frac{d\theta}{dt} \right) \right)$.

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\ln(1 - e^2 \cos(\theta)^2) \right) = \frac{2e^2 \cos(\theta(t)) \sin(\theta(t))}{1 - e^2 \cos(\theta(t))} \cdot \frac{d\theta}{dt}$$

Thus, the equation takes the form:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\ln \left(\frac{d\theta}{dt} \right) \right) = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\ln(1 - e^2 \cos(\theta)^2) \right) \quad (2.4)$$

Integrating with respect to time, we obtain:

$$\ln \left(\frac{d\theta}{dt} \right) = \ln(1 - e^2 \cos(\theta)^2) + \ln C$$

where C is the constant of integration. Simplifying:

$$\frac{d\theta}{dt} = C(1 - e^2 \cos(\theta)^2) \quad (2.5)$$

Using the expression for the radius $r(\theta(t)) = \frac{b}{\sqrt{1-e^2 \cos^2 \theta(t)}} \rightarrow r^2 = \frac{b^2}{1-e^2 \cos(\theta)^2}$ and computing derivatives, we find that the sectorial velocity is constant:

$$r^2 \frac{d\theta}{dt} = \frac{b^2}{1-e^2 \cos(\theta)^2} \cdot C(1 - e^2 \cos(\theta)^2) = Cb^2. \quad (2.6)$$

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = \frac{1}{2} r^2 \frac{d\theta}{dt} = \frac{1}{2} Cb^2 = \text{const.} \quad (2.7)$$

Kepler's Third Law

Using the angular velocity, radius, and sectorial velocity, the third law is derived by analogy with the focal case. Since there are no perihelion and aphelion points, two characteristic points of the orbit are chosen where the angular acceleration is zero: the ends of the major and minor axes.

$$\theta = 0, r = a, \dot{\theta} = C(1 - e^2), v_a = r\dot{\theta} = aC(1 - e^2)$$

$$\theta = \frac{\pi}{2}, r = b, \dot{\theta} = C, v_b = r\dot{\theta} = bC$$

Expression of constant C in terms of period T

Area of an ellipse: $S = \pi ab$

$$S = \frac{dA}{dt} T \rightarrow \pi ab = \frac{1}{2} Cb^2 T$$

$$\text{it follows from this } C = \frac{2\pi a}{bT} \quad (2.8)$$

$$\Delta v = v_b - v_a = \frac{2\pi a}{bT} (b - a(1 - e^2))$$

$$T = \frac{2\pi a}{b\Delta v} (b - a(1 - e^2))$$

We use the geometric relationship for the ellipse:

$$b^2 = a^2(1 - e^2) \rightarrow b = a\sqrt{1 - e^2}$$

The resulting expression for the period is:

$$T = \frac{2\pi a \cdot a\sqrt{1-e^2}(1-\sqrt{1-e^2})}{a\sqrt{1-e^2} \cdot \Delta v} = \frac{2\pi a \cdot (1-\sqrt{1-e^2})}{\Delta v} \quad (2.9)$$

Numerical examples again confirm agreement with Kepler's third law.

Example 1. Let us set $a = 9$; $b = 7$.

$$a = 9.00, b = 7.00$$

$$e = 0.62853938$$

$$r_a = 9.0 \quad r_b = 7.0$$

$$v_a = 1.628974 \quad v_b = 2.007179$$

$$T = \sqrt{a^3} = 27.000000$$

$$T = \frac{2\pi a(1-\sqrt{1-e^2})}{(v_b-v_a)} = 27$$

$$27.000000 \approx 26.999981$$

Example 2. Mercury

$$a = 0.39 \text{ [au]}, b = 0.38 \text{ [au]}$$

$$T = \sqrt{a^3} = 0.24084271 \text{ [Earth year]}$$

$$T = \frac{2\pi a(1-\sqrt{1-e^2})}{(v_b-v_a)} = 0.240842301 \text{ [Earth year]}$$

$$0.24084271 \approx 0.240842301 \text{ [Earth year]}$$

Example 3. Venus

$$a = 0.73 \text{ [au]}, b = 0.73 \text{ [au]}$$

$$e = 6.80000009\text{E-}03$$

$$T = \sqrt{a^3} = 0.62144679 \text{ [Earth year]}$$

$$T = \frac{2\pi a(1-\sqrt{1-e^2})}{(v_b-v_a)} = 0.62116992 \text{ [Earth year]}$$

$$0.62144679 \approx 0.62116992 \text{ [Earth year]}$$

Example 4. Earth

$$a = 1.00 \text{ [au]}, b = 0.99986297 \text{ [au]}$$

$$e = 1.67112295\text{E-}02$$

$$T = \sqrt{a^3} = 1.0000039 \text{ [Earth year]}$$

$$T = \frac{2\pi a(1-\sqrt{1-e^2})}{(v_b-v_a)} = 1.0000157 \text{ [Earth year]}$$

$$1.0000039 \approx 1.0000157 \text{ [Earth year]}$$

Example 5. Mars

$$a = 1.52 \text{ [au]}, b = 1.52 \text{ [au]}$$

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$$T = \sqrt{a^3} = 1.8807580 \text{ [Earth year]}$$

$$T = \frac{2\pi a(1-\sqrt{1-e^2})}{(v_b-v_a)} = 1.8807570 \text{ [Earth year]}$$

$$1.8807580 \approx 1.8807570 \text{ [Earth year]}$$

III. Motion Relative to an Arbitrary Origin

The radius formula relative to the focus (1.2) and relative to the center (2.3) are two different parameterizations of the same curve—the ellipse. Their equivalence follows from the general equation of the ellipse and coordinate transformations when shifting the origin.

Mathematically, any point in the plane can be chosen as the origin, and the corresponding equations of motion can be derived. In each such system, analogues of Kepler's laws—the law of areas and the relation between the period and geometric parameters—can be obtained.

Conclusion

Mathematically, Kepler's laws are properties of the kinematic equations of motion along conic sections (curves of the second order).

This means that:

1. The choice of the origin is arbitrary—we can place it at any point in the plane (the focus, the center, inside the ellipse, or even outside the ellipse).
2. After transforming the equations (parameterizing, recalculating the radius and angle), we obtain a new kinematic equation that describes motion along the same curve, but relative to the new pole.